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Expert Statement by Prof. Dr. Seideman on Neuroendocrine Patterns in Patients with Mitochondriopathies and/or Autonomic Dysfunctions

Observational Insights on Neuroendocrine Patterns in Mitochondriopathies and other Rare Diseases

In my career as a neuroendocrinologist, focusing on rare and complex cases, I have identified unique patterns in patients suffering from mitochondriopathies, particularly those causing autonomic dysfunctions as a complication. While a comprehensive study is underway to validate these findings scientifically, the urgency of the clinical situation compels me to share these preliminary insights.

The full study, expected to take an additional three years or more, will adhere to stringent scientific standards.

However, given the severe implications for patients currently suffering and the potential mortality associated with these conditions, there exists a moral imperative to disseminate these observations now.

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Observational Patterns

Pancreas dysregulation and/or PDH cytopathy imitating Diabetes: In cases that present with diabetes-like symptoms (elevated blood glucose) but are not diabetes per se, I have constantly been observing a significant positive response to the corticosteroid Prednisolone. This is entirely contrary to established medical understanding but has been a consistent finding across numerous patient cases.

Noradrenalin storms can be calmed down with the mixture of three medications: The combination of intramuscular Tramadol with Procain and Dimetindene has shown to be by far the most effective noradrenalin modulator encountered in my practice. This combination has demonstrated perplexing efficacy in modulating not desired autonomic responses.

Adrenaline reduction: Alprazolam (Xanax) has been the only medication observed to reduce adrenaline synthesis in the renal medulla by approximately 50%. This finding is significant, given the lack of effective alternatives in current medical practice. Breier and colleagues understood this already in 1992.

Homeostasis restoration in highly acute autonomic dysfunction: In cascading episodes of autonomic dysfunction, a combination of midazolam and diazepam have been the most effective combination of drugs in restoring homeostasis. This approach, while unconventional and far from harmless, has shown strong positive outcomes in acute crisis management in uncountable cases.

Pseudo-diabetes: Not everything that looks like diabetes is a case of diabetes. Pseudo-diabetes, a clinical syndrome characterized by often erratically dysregulated glucose levels, most commonly found in patients exhibiting altered catecholamine function or other autonomic dysfunctions, which often manifest in asynchronous patterns, such as those observed in gastroparesis or the aberrant release of insulin. A novel approach in these select cases involves the administration of a compound injection comprising 50-100 mg Tramadol, 4-8 mg Dimetindene, 30-60 mg Procain, and 3-5 mg Midazolam. Despite the very severe risks associated with this pharmacological blend, it has already shown significant efficacy in several small patient cohorts ($n < 5$), with robust, sustained effects and - very important - so far obviously without evidence of tolerance development. Given the very high potential risks, initiation of this treatment regimen, also referred to as Amitradicain, is recommended within a controlled inpatient hospital setting equipped with emergency care facilities. The therapeutic effect manifests rapidly post-intramuscular injection and remains stable for 3 to 5 hours. It is critical to note that Amitradicain is contraindicated in patients with conventional diabetes mellitus. On the other hand, patients with pseudo-diabetes resultant from autonomic dysautonomia exhibit a reduced response to standard diabetic treatments, including insulin.

Clinical Implications and Future Directions

These patterns, emerging from hundreds of patient cases under my direct or co-treatment, challenge conventional medical paradigms, especially the use of Prednisolone for pseudo-diabetes and the application of potent, potentially addictive compounds in such contexts. My forthcoming paper will delve into these patterns in detail, providing the necessary scientific and clinical context.

In the interim, it is crucial for medical professionals treating patients with rare diseases to be aware of these findings. While they deviate extremely from

standard protocols, they represent a potential lifeline for patients suffering from these complex conditions. This statement is intended to spark further investigation and highly cautious application with many risks in clinical practice, always prioritizing patient safety and informed consent.

Conclusion

The patterns I have observed and outlined are preliminary but grounded in extensive clinical experience. I urge the medical community to consider these observations as potential avenues for treatment, particularly in cases where conventional approaches have proven ineffective. The ultimate goal is to alleviate suffering and improve outcomes for patients with these challenging conditions.

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Conflicts of interest

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